

ASSESSMENT OF THE PROPERTIES OF AIR ON THE STATE OF THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE OF THE DUODENUM IN PATIENTS WITH PEPTIC ULCER WITH ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION AND DIABETES TYPE 2

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Abstract

The article highlights the changes in the mucous membrane of the duodenum in patients with peptic ulcer with arterial hypertension and diabetes type 2, namely a decrease in the secretion of protective mucus. Given the healing properties of air, it can be said that air is an additional remedy in the treatment of duodenal ulcers.

Keywords: ulcer, diabetes, hypertension, air.

Introduction. Peptic ulcer (PV) remains one of the most common nosological forms of modern gastroenterology (in Ukraine the prevalence is 7-10 % [1]. In recent years, the frequency of combination of peptic gastric ulcer (PVS) and duodenum has increased with other organs) with other organs) and systems, in particular in 22% of PVS patients, hypertension (hypertension) was detected [2], and in 17.5% of patients - diabetes type 2 (CD2) [3].

A certain group of pathogens associated with rapid atherosclerosis (AU), insulin resistance (IP) and hyperinsulinemia (GI) has been identified. These include representatives of the Herpetoviridae family (including CMV, HSV-1, EBV), Chlamydia pneumoniae, Helicobacter pylori (N.Pylori), Porfiromonas gingivalis [4]. The occurrence of endothelial damage due to the direct effect of H. pylori and stimulation of systemic and local inflammation is known [1]. At the same time, the ways of realization of H. pylori on the cardiovascular and endocrine systems are not fully understood [2].

The purpose of the study is to investigate the phytotherapeutic effect of air in the peptic ulcer of the duodenum, combined with arterial hypertension and diabetes type 2.

Research methods. As a result of screening, 120 patients with HP-associated PVS and DPC aged 18 to 75 years (an average of $48.81 \pm 1,42$) were involved in the study. 67 patients with concomitant hypertension (hypertension) and diabetes type 2 (CD2). Among the sick men were 70 (58.3%), women - 50 (41.7%). The control group consisted of 30 practically healthy persons (PCOs) (men - 22, women - 8) in which no acute and chronic diseases were detected at the time of examination of acute and chronic diseases. We also selected 24 patients with chronic non-atrophic gastritis (HNAG) associated with HR, incl. 11 patients with concomitant hypertension and CD2 (men -12 (50%), women -12 (50%)).

All patients were in hospital treatment in the gastroenterology department of the Chernivtsi Regional Clinical Hospital and Chernivtsi Regional Endocrinology Center in 2013-2016.

The presence of PVS and DPK was verified on the basis of a clinical picture, anamnesis data, objective methods of examination of the patient, the results of endoscopic and morphological studies of SOS and DPK.

Determination of the stage and degree of hypertension (AH) was carried out in accordance with the criteria recommended in 2013 by the European Society for Hypertension (ESH) / European Society of Cardiologists (ESC). Diagnosis of CD 2 was made according to the WHO standards 2006/2011 (HBA1C > 6.5 %, plasma glucose ≥ 7.0 mmol/l, postprandial glycemia after 2 hours ≥ 11.0 mmol/l).

Diagnosis was carried out in accordance with the national recommendations of the unified clinical protocol of primary, emergency and secondary (specialized) medical care to patients with PVS and DPK in adults, approved by the order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine No. 613 of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine dated 03.09.2014; Unified clinical protocol of primary, emergency and secondary (specialized) medical care to patients with hypertension, approved by the order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine No. 384, dated 24.05.2012 and recommendations of the European Society of Cardiology (European of Hypertension) and ECETY. ology - ESC) (2013); Unified Protocol "On Approval and Implementation of Medical and Technological Documents on Standardization of Medical Aid in type 2 diabetes" Order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine No. 1118 of 21.12.2012.

Criteria for inclusion in the study: male and female patients over 18 years of age with verified peptic gastric ulcer and duodenum associated with toxigenic (CAGA, VACA) strains of H.pylori, including combined with arterial hypertension, I-I-I-I-II. Stage II, diabetes 2 of mild and moderate severity, subcompensated and compensated.

To verify the diagnosis of Khnag, PV of the stomach and DPK, fibrogastroduodenoscopy was performed using the GIF Q-40 apparatus Olympus (Japan) with a target biopsy according to the conventional method. Characteristics of endoscopic changes of the gastric and duodenum mucosa were carried out with the use of minimal standard terminology. Inflammatory and atrophic changes were evaluated by degrees: 0 - absence of signs, 1 - minimum degree, 2 - moderate and 3 - pronounced.

Diagnosis of HP was performed using a rapid urease test with biopsy material, production of polymerase chain reaction (PCR) with biopsy and urease respiratory test using the Helik test system with indicator tubes

("AMA"). *Helicobacter pylori* DNA was isolated from the antral stomach biopsies using special DNA sets ("Litich". Russia). CAGA and VACA *Helicobacter Pylori* were determined by biopsy with the help of Helikopol reagents. The intensity of the signal in the gel was determined by the following criteria: weak signal (+), moderate signal (++) , strong signal (+++). The results with a weak, moderate and strong signal were taken into development. The evaluation of the detection of *H.pylori* CAGA and VACA genes and their alleles was carried out according to the instructions, namely the presence of a DNA fragment of the CAGA 404 DNA.

light filter and VACA (allele S1+S2, M1, M2) for 259 pcs. +286 PN, 290 p. and 352 p. in accordance.

The level of glycemia was investigated by the glucose oxidase method using standard kits of reagents of production of NPP "Philisit Diagnosis" (Ukraine). Glycosylated hemoglobin (HBA1C) was determined using a photolorimetric method using a set of reagents of Spinelab (Kharkiv, Ukraine).

Research results. On the basis of the color of hematoxylin and eosin drugs, other morphometric parameters of the SODPC state were obtained, the data of which are given in Tables 1-2

Table 1

Morphometric indicators of the mucous membrane in patients with peptic ulcer of the duodenum without concomitant pathology, $M \pm m$

Indicators	cagA+vacA+ n=11	cagA+ ađo vacA+ n=7
Enterocyte desquamation (points: 0 to 5)	2,4±0,05	1,8±0,04 p<0,05
The percentage of vessels with phenomena of stasis and (or) Suppress erythrocytes (%)	32,0±1,6	7,0±0,4 p<0,05
Stroma edema (points: 0 to 5)	3,7±0,07	1,2±0,02 p<0,05
Hemorrhage in stroma (points: 0 to 5)	2,4±0,05	1,1±0,02 p<0,05
The degree of infiltration of PMAL (points: 0 to 5)	2,8±0,07	1,1±0,04 p<0,05
Percentage of glass cells (%)	14,0±0,9	24,0±1,2 p<0,05

Note. P <0.05 - the reliability of differences between these groups.

Table 2

Morphometric parameters of the mucous membrane in patients with peptic ulcer of the duodenum in combination with arterial hypertension and diabetes type 2, $M \pm m$

Indicators	cagA+vacA+ n=9	cagA+ ađo vacA+ n=17
Enterocyte desquamation (points: 0 to 5)	3,2±0,05	2,0±0,04 p<0,05
The percentage of vessels with phenomena of stasis and (or) Suppress erythrocytes (%)	39,0±1,6	19,0±0,4 p<0,05
Stroma edema (points: 0 to 5)	3,9±0,07	2,8±0,02 p<0,05
Hemorrhage in stroma (points: 0 to 5)	2,9±0,05	1,8±0,02 p<0,05
The degree of infiltration of PMAL (points: 0 to 5)	3,9±0,08	2,1±0,05 p<0,05
Percentage of glass cells (%)	12,0±0,8	21,0±1,1 p<0,05

Note. P <0.05 - the reliability of differences between these groups.

In general, the analysis of these tables allows to conclude that CAGA+ VACA+ Patients The condition of the SODPC is worse than that of CAGA+ or VACA+ patients. This is especially evident in the manifestations of inflammatory reactions, which are evaluated not only by the level of inflammatory infiltration by polymorphonuclear leukocytes (PMAAL), but also taking into account such phenomena of exudation as edema of stroma, blood stasis and erythrocyte, hemorrhage. The level of desquamation of the cover epithelium indicated the level of alternation (damage) of these cells. In patients with peptic ulcer with hypertension and CD2, SODPK damage was more pronounced.

From ancient times, people have known that Air has a lot of healing properties. This plant is very often used in folk medicine.

Rhizomes include from 1.5 to 3% of essential oil. It contains A-Pinen, acorin, aromatic compounds, organic acids, ascorbic acid, choline, tannins, starch, iodine, resin, azarildehyde, vitamins B and C. The main active components are campfire, boar, cafneol, camphor, sescol.

Its leaves also contain many tannins and essential oils. This oil consists of a mixture of Terpens and Seskviterpens, Azarildeidov, which provides a specific smell. And in the rhizome of the tortoise there is a small

amount of fragrant soap, vitamins, protein, starch and minerals. Decoction of this plant can be taken for the treatment of stomach pain. The roots have an action that increases appetite, perfectly improves digestion, enhances the reflex separation of all gastric juice. Today, marsh marsh is used in folk medicine as a good remedy for the treatment of peptic ulcer.

Pharmacological action. Due to these substances in the composition of the roots of marshmallows, they stimulate metabolism, normalize the digestive processes and production of secretory liquids. Vitamin C in the composition of vegetable raw materials provides nutrition to the body's cells, has a positive effect on the tone and ability of the body to withstand infectious and viral disease, the negative effects of the environment. In addition to the ability to strengthen the immunity, the root of the tortoise stimulates the work of neurons, because it contains vitamin B4. The component has a soothing and neuroprotective effect on the body. Palmitic acid, which is part of the roots, eliminates inflammation and has wound healing properties. The plant also has a bacteriostatic effect.

Air common is a herbaceous plant that can reach a height of 60 cm to 1.2 meters. It has a long (up to 1.5 meters) creeping rhizome, horizontally located, with numerous thin roots branched from it. They are thin and mich. The rhizome is spongy, in the section white with a slight pink tinge, gives out a pleasant aroma. The root leaves of the plant is cut-shaped, its length reaches one meter. Outwardly, the leaves of the plant resembles an iris. Air of marsh erect stem. On the one hand it is flattened, on the other - has a sharp face. Due to this in the cross section it is triangular. Air is covered with small flowers of greenish -yellow hue, which form inflorescences - cobs. Fruits the plant with red berries. In Ukraine and neighboring countries, the plant multiplies mainly by rhizomes, since in the temperate climatic zone, the fruits of air are rarely ripened.

It is widely used as aromatic bitterness, increases appetite and improves digestion.

Conclusion. Given the condition of the mucous membrane of the duodenum, combined with arterial hypertension and diabetes type 2 diabetes and the healing properties of the air can be said that Air should be used in the treatment of this pathology.

References

1. Singh RK, McMahon AD, Patel H, Packard CJ, Rathbone BJ, Samani NJ. Prospective analysis of the association of infection with CagA bearing strains of *Helicobacter pylori* and coronary heart disease. *Heart*. 2002 Jul;88(1):43-6.
2. Skvarc M, Kopitar AN, Kos J, Obermajer N, Tepes B. Differences in the antigens of *Helicobacter pylori* strains influence on the innate immune response in the in vitro experiments. *Mediators Inflamm*. 2014; 287531. doi: 10.1155/2014/287531. [<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3927579/>].
3. Zou J, Dong J, Yu X. Meta-analysis: Lactobacillus containing quadruple therapy versus standard triple first-line therapy for *Helicobacter pylori* eradication. *Helicobacter*. 2009 Oct;14(5):97-107. doi: 10.1111/j.1523-5378.2009.00716.x.
4. Zullo A, Ierardi E, Hassan C, de Francesco V. Furazolidone-based therapies for *Helicobacter pylori* infection: a pooled-data analysis. *Saudi J Gastroenterol*. 2012 Jan-Feb;18(1):11-7. doi: 10.4103/1319-3767.91729
5. Zullo A, Hassan C, Ridola L, De Francesco V, Vaira D. Standard triple and sequential therapies for *Helicobacter pylori* eradication: an update. *Eur J Intern Med*. 2013 Jan;24(1):16-9. doi: 10.1016/j.ejim.2012.07.006. [<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28681177>].